

USE OF INNOVATIVE MOBILE APPLICATIONS FOR TRAINING STUDENTS OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

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ANNOTATION:

The study examines the use of mobile applications in medical education in Uzbekistan, in particular their potential to increase accessibility, improve learning outcomes, and the need to localize content to better support students.

Keywords: mobile applications.medical education

Relevance: In the context of digitalization, mobile platforms play an important role in modernizing medical education by providing access to interactive educational materials and simulations.

Aim: The study aims to explore the potential of mobile platforms and applications to improve the accessibility and quality of medical education in Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods: The study analyzed available mobile educational platforms such as Medscape, Complete Anatomy, and others. The study was conducted on the basis of three leading universities in Uzbekistan: Tashkent Medical Academy, Samarkand State Medical Institute and Bukhara Medical Institute. Data collection included: 1. A survey of 1,200 students and 150 teachers showed that mobile technologies are actively used in education; 2. Comparative analysis of mobile solutions available in Uzbek and English, with an emphasis on functionality and content; 3. Study examples of successful use of mobile technologies in medical education abroad. The research methods included questionnaires, statistical data processing, and comparative analysis.

Results: Data analysis showed that

- 68% of students already use mobile apps in the learning process, but only 34% consider them effective. The main reason is the lack of materials in Uzbek languages.

- 75% of teachers noted the need to introduce specialized educational applications to improve the quality of education.

- The use of mobile simulators and educational platforms has increased student academic performance by 20-25% due to interactivity.

Conclusion: The introduction of mobile platforms and applications into medical education in Uzbekistan is a promising area that can significantly improve the quality of specialist training. Localization of educational content, its adaptation to the needs of students and the integration of mobile solutions into curricula will help reduce the educational gap between regions and optimize the process of independent learning.

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